

Consent in Experiments Involving Human Participants

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Imagine you are part of a group of researchers who are conducting an experiment on human-robot interaction. The data that you are working with is audio and video data collected by the robot during its interactions with the human participants. The participants are in advance asked for written consent for this data to be analyzed for research purposes. During the experiment, the participants are also, by way of a researcher raising their hand, made aware at which point the robot starts saving the data. However, after all the data has been collected and analyzed, you realize that the researcher who was supposed to raise their hand, did so only a few minutes after they were supposed to. This means that participants had only really given consent for part of the collected data to be used.

Now imagine that the researcher who failed to raise their hand is a PhD student called Sophie. Sophie feels bad about what happened and tries to convince her supervisor, who is also involved in the experiment, that they need to ask the participants to renew their consent. Sophie's supervisor strongly disagrees as this would mean missing the deadline to an influential conference that is approaching. The supervisor plans to submit a paper on the experiment either way and threatens to exclude Sophie from the paper if she tells anyone outside the research group about what has happened. This would be a hard blow for Sophie as she needs the publication for her PhD dissertation.

Questions:

1. From an ethical point of view, should the researchers inform the participants that recording started earlier than they were told, potentially risking that some participants will withdraw their consent or might not respond in time for the conference deadline?
2. In what ways is Sophie's supervisor misusing the power imbalance between them, and what should Sophie do?